

ARE VIDEOS AND AUDIOS ALL-IMPORTANT IN ESP CLASSES? HOW AND HOW MUCH OF THEM TO INCORPORATE IN TEACHING ESP CLASSES

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Introduction

The importance of including video and audio in teaching legal English. As soon as audio recording and video equipment were invented, people started using them for different reasons, military, music, advertisement, commercial purposes. It was not until the early 20th century, it became an important part of any language learning textbook. However, English for Specific Purposes (ESP) always lacked audio-video materials, particularly the Legal English sphere. It is widely believed that we can no longer teach any courses with just a textbook.

Most language teachers believe that video and audio contents are interesting and they motivate students. (Cakir, 2006). He also

ABSTRACT

This research paper analyses the importance of video and audio materials in teaching ESP, particularly legal English. The author conducts surveys among both teachers and law students. As part of the research, students wrote summaries based on the lessons with and without these materials. The author explores the challenges and the difficulties ESP teachers face in incorporating video & audio materials as well as analyzing the students' views on these materials in the classes.

states that audios and videos are authentic and contextualized classroom environments.

According to Cakir (2006), language instructors find the video content both interesting and motivating as it creates a real, contextualized, and the authentic teaching-learning environment.

However, textbooks still only include a few short audios without any videos even in the second decade of the 21st century. In this research paper, the author conducts a survey among 20 ESP teachers at the foreign language department of Tashkent State Law University and 100 students as well as writing tasks to check how video and audio materials affected their learning.

Literature review

ideo and audio materials are relatively new in teaching ESP. Therefore, the research on these areas is also quite novel. The author selects the research which contributed most to the field. Muhammad Alhaj (2020) believes that video materials help the students to retain the information better because of visual aid. Using audio & video materials is a vital part of ESP because if they are at the appropriate level, they create interest in the subject and make the students more confident in communicative competence as well as making the lessons more engaging (Neda Radosavlevikj, 2019). As Violeta Jurkovič (2015) states video & audio materials are seen as 'peripheral' in teaching ESP which needs to be researched more and it is expected that students and ESP teachers will benefit from the use of these materials.

Methods

In this research, the author used two methods of research: survey and writing tasks to check and analyze the effectiveness of the video and audio materials.

First of all, 20 ESP teachers at the foreign language department were asked questions about the effectiveness of these materials.

Teachers were asked 3 questions about including video & audio materials in teaching legal English. The first question was about the effectiveness of these materials. The second question was an open-ended question about the challenges teachers face when using or finding these materials. The last question was on how much proportion of the lessons should audio & video materials be used in teaching legal English.

Students were also asked 3 questions about the use of these materials. The questions included questions such as "do you think video/audio materials make the lessons more interesting?", "What are the challenges you face with these materials?"

"If you are asked to read a page of a coursebook or watch a 5-minute video, which one would you do?"

Students were asked to write a summary of the lessons. As a part of the research, there were 3 lessons conducted with audio & video materials and 3 lessons without these materials, mainly using the textbook. After each three lessons students are asked to write a summary of the lessons to see how much they understood the lesson and how interesting the lesson has been conducted.

The summary questions were as follows:

1. What did you learn in the lesson?
2. How was the lesson interesting/boring?
3. What do you think about the materials used in the classroom?
4. What are the challenges you faced during the lesson?
5. If you could change, what would you change in this lesson, why?

These questions helped to analyze and find out the importance of the video & audio materials and the challenges students face with audio materials. Moreover, what should ESP teachers do to make the learning enjoyable and achieve the objectives of the lesson?

Results

Results were pretty interesting and there were some unexpected results as well.

When asked about the effectiveness of the video & audio materials,

80% of the teachers chose the option of “effective” when asked about the

effectiveness of these materials. While 10% of them chose the option of “I am not sure”, and 10% “no”, respectively.

Graph 1 (Do you think video & audio materials are effective in teaching legal English?)

In open ended questions, teachers wrote about their challenges they face while teaching legal English. One of the teacher wrote “It is time-consuming to find a video which is at the right level for my students”. Another teacher says “I have 4 groups of sophomore students, all of them are at different level from beginner to advanced, I need to find these materials at four levels, for which I do not have adequate time and energy”. Another experienced teacher wrote “Finding related video or audio is difficult and what is more difficult and time-consuming is I need to watch them beforehand to make sure that there is no culture-sensitive materials in them”. Other teachers wrote about the technological challenges such as the lack of speakers in the classrooms and teachers

have to bring with them, computers do not support certain video and audio formats, etc.

Critics of the usage of video & audio materials believes that while conducting video & audio enriched lessons, teachers forget about textbook exercises which will be in midterms and final exams.

The last but not least, when asked about how much of video & audio materials should consist of the lesson, 20% of the ESP teachers at the department believe

They should not exceed more than 10% of all materials. Another 20% of the teachers believe they should be more than 50%, while the majority of teachers (60%) think audio & video materials must be between 20-30%.

Graph 2 How much should the audio & video materials be used in teaching legal English?

When it comes to students' responses, they were interesting to find out and quite unexpected as well.

100% of the students think video & audio materials make the Legal English lessons interesting.

Graph 3 Do you think video & audio materials make the lessons interesting?

When asked about the challenges that students face when these materials are used in the classroom, one learner wrote "In some videos they speak too fast that I can't understand them, in other videos they speak so slow". Another student says "They are not at my level, I mostly face difficulty with understanding the whole meaning, I

have to listen to them 3-4 times, but the teacher only plays once in the class". The other students wrote "The people in the video speak in different accents which I find them difficult to fully comprehend. Moreover, some of them speak too fast". Other students wrote about the difficulties of the videos and audios to understand

different varieties of the English spoken by the speakers and the words that are used in the video which students do not understand.

When students were asked to choose to read a page from the textbook or watch/listen to 5 minutes audio/video, 85% of the students went with the latter one.

Graph 4 Do you prefer to read a page from your textbook or listen/watch 5 minutes audio/video.

In terms of summaries, 50% of students who participated in lessons without these materials did not complete the task fully or at all. On the other hand, after video & audio enriched classes, this figure was just 5%. Mostly students mentioned about the length of the teacher talk, boring multiple choice activities, ec. Majority of them wrote a couple of legal vocabularies when they were asked on what they learned. On the other hand, students wrote more and elaborated on every question of the summaries, they mentioned about the authenticity of the materials, different accents and people. Most of the students were satisfied with the materials used in the classroom saying they were engaging.

Discussion

From the results of the research, it can be seen that video & audio materials are a must in ESP classes. From the teachers'

responses, it can be concluded that most of these teachers feel that these materials are important when delivering the lessons but as the textbooks do not contain such important elements, they find it time-consuming and difficult to adapt to their classes. While almost all teachers believe these materials should be in all classes, the proportion of video & audio materials is a question most of them think differently. However, more than half of the teachers think 20-30% is a good range.

When it comes to students' surveys, the majority of them have a positive attitude towards the use of these materials in their classes, however, they find them challenging for various reasons.

In terms of summary results, it is evident that after video & audio enriched lessons, students wrote more and elaborated in all summary questions compared to the ones

which did not include any of them in which half of the students could not complete the summaries.

In conclusion, it can be said that video and audios are an important part of materials in ESP, particularly in teaching legal English. Material designers should consider this when creating coursebooks. ESP teachers should also be cautious in choosing the appropriate level of these materials so that students understand them. If needed teachers are advised to give the scripts of the videos and the audios.

Limitations

The research was conducted with 20 ESP teachers who teach legal English which may not apply to all ESP areas. The number of students was just 100 which is good enough but researchers may get different results if they conduct the research with larger groups of students. Last but not least, only 3 lessons were compared which means there can be huge differences when the whole course is conducted in one or other modalities.

REFERENCES:

1. Ali Albashir Mohammed Alhaj Using Pedagogic Video to Enhance English for Specific Purposes Teaching Program (ESP)for Saudi University Students: A New Prospective Approach
2. Ismail çakır The use of video as an audio-visual material in foreign language teaching classroom
3. Neda Radosavlevikj (2019) Using Video Presentations in ESP Classes (A Study Conducted at the Language Centre-Skopje, SEEU)
4. Violeta Jurkovič (2015) Pedagogical uses of authentic video in ESP classrooms for developing language skills and enriching vocabulary
5. Miraziz, R., & Oybek, T. (2020). INGLIZ, FRANSUZ VA O'ZBEK SHE'RIYATINI TARJIMA QILISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN TRANSFORMATSIYALAR. Oriental Art and Culture, (V).
6. Raufov, M. M. (2021). ELEMENTARY TRANSFORMATIONS IN SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(1).
7. Mamadayupova, V. S. (2015). Application of information technologies in the course of training in the foreign language. *European Journal of Education and Applied Psychology*, (1), 6-8.
8. Shonazarovna, M. V. (2019). Some ways of learning foreign language at an early age. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(10).
9. Mirgiyazova, M. M. (2021). THE ROLE OF DISCOURSE ANALYSIS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2).
10. Umida Pulatovna Khaydarova (2021). Intercultural communication as a pattern of learning content in linguocultural competence. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2 (1), 783-788.

11. Khaydarova, U. The Use Of Interactive Technologies And Methods In Online Practical Lessons In Uzbekistan During Covid-19 Pandemic. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(03), 2020.
12. Khaydarova, U. (2019). Spiritual, social, philosophical and poetic factors of the detective genre. *Humanities in the 21st century: scientific problems and searching for effective humanist technologies*. 69-72
13. Khaydarova, U., Mustafaeva, N., & Abdurakhmonov, B. (2020). ISSUES ON ENCREASING MOTIVATION IN LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(05), 1479-1482.
14. Yusupova Sh. Qizi, Y. S. T. (2020). Religious speech and phonetic interference. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 679-683.
15. Yusupova, Shahzoda Tokhirjon kizi (2019) "STUDY OF RELIGIOUS FUNCTIONAL STYLE IN THE WORLD LINGUISTICS," *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University: Vol. 1 : Iss. 12 , Article 32*.
16. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/namdu/vol1/iss12/32>
17. Yusupova Sh. Diniy matnlarda illokutiv aktning namoyon bo'lishi//<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4963456>
18. Yusupova Sh. Diniy matnlarning lingvopragmatik tadqiqi//
<https://library.ziyonet.uz/ru/book/114021>
19. 南山言語科学 = Nanzan studies in language science (16), 1-26, 2021-03